

TEMPORAL VARIATION IN ARRIVAL AND PRICES OF DRY CHILLI IN MAJOR MARKETS OF INDIA.

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Abstract

This research examines the temporal variation in the arrival and prices of dry chilli across five major Indian markets Guntur, Byadgi, Khammam, Warangal, and Nandurbar spanning the period from 2012 to 2022. The study employs key analytical tools such as Compound Growth Rate (CGR), Coefficient of Variation, Cuddy-Della Index, as well as seasonal and cyclical indices to identify trends and variations. The CGR reveals higher growth rates in Guntur (2.25%) and Warangal (3.46%), highlighting their prominence in the market. Seasonal patterns indicate peak arrivals in March and the lowest in July across all markets. Additionally, cyclical indices suggest a consistent downward trend in both arrivals and prices over the decade, pointing to cyclical variations. Correlation analysis shows that Guntur and Byadgi have stable positive correlations, while Nandurbar exhibits negative correlations, suggesting a greater influence of external factors on this market. These findings provide valuable insights into the dynamic nature of chilli markets, offering a foundation for strategic recommendations to manage future market fluctuations effectively.

Keywords: CGR, Arrivals, Prices, Constraints, Dry Chilli, Coefficient, Variations

Introduction and Objectives:

The Temporal variation in the Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli in major Indian markets such as Guntur, Byadgi, Khammam, Warangal and Nandurbar, is a critical area of study due to its significant impact on both producers and consumers. These markets, being key hubs for Dry Chilli trade, exhibit distinct patterns in terms of supply and pricing influenced by various factors including seasonal production cycles, weather conditions, and market demand. Understanding these variations is essential for developing effective strategies to stabilize prices and ensure a steady supply, thereby benefiting farmers and consumers alike. The study is designed to analyse Trends, Seasonal fluctuations, inter-annual variations, Cyclical indices, and Correlations in Dry Chilli arrivals and prices across these markets, offering insights that could guide policymaking and market interventions.

The specific objectives of the study are:

- 1) To study the trend and variations in arrival and prices of dry chilli.
- 2) To workout seasonal indices of arrival and prices of dry chilli.
- 3) To Estimate the cyclical indices of arrival and prices of dry chilli
- 4) To study the relationship between arrival and prices of dry chilli.

Materials and Methods

The collected data were systematically analyzed and results were tabulated to facilitate the generalization of key findings, allowing for meaningful inferences. Various statistical and econometric tools were employed based on the study's objectives and the nature of the data. These tools include the Compound Growth Rate (CGR) to assess the growth trends in arrivals and prices, and measures of variability to evaluate fluctuations in both. Seasonal indices were used to capture recurring patterns throughout the year, while cyclical indices helped identify longer-term trends. Finally, correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between arrivals and prices, offering insights into their interdependence.

Tools of analysis

To study the Trend and Variation in Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli .

The variability in Arrival Prices of Dry Chilli during selected period is calculated by using following formula.

Compound Growth Rate:

In present study the compound growth rates in production and yield of Dry Chilli estimated as follows :

The exponential equation of the following type was used :

$$Y=ab^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where ,

Y = Arrival and Prices,

a = Intercept or Constant,

b = Trend coefficient/Regression

t = Time variable.

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follow:

$$\text{Log } y = \text{Log } a + t \text{ log } b \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Annual compound growth rate in percentage was calculated as

$$\text{CGR}(\%) = [\text{Antilog of } (\text{log } b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

To estimate the trend in arrival and prices the data was smoothened by moving average method or by data transformation. The trend was estimated by original graphical method and moving average method.

Co-efficient of variation:

Coefficient of variation in Arrival and Prices was computed to see the variation and predict the behaviour of prices and arrival whether they are stable involving less risk and uncertainty and vice-versa.

$$C.V = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}} \times 100$$

Where,

σ = Standard deviation

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x-\bar{x})^2}{n}}$$

$\bar{x}$ = Arithmetic mean in

x = Variable

n = Number of observations

Cuddy-Della Valle instability Index (CDVI):

To check the variability in Arrival and Prices, coefficient of variation (CV) and Cuddy-Della Valle instability index (CDVI) was used ,as follows:

$$\text{CDVI} (\%) = \text{CV} \sqrt{(1 - R)^2}$$

Where,

C.V = Coefficient of Variation

= Adjusted coefficient of multiple determination

To workout Seasonal Indices in Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli

The Seasonal indices of Arrival and Prices of an Dry Chilli was worked out by using the simple moving average method.

$$SI = \frac{\text{Monthly average of arrival and prices}}{\text{Average of monthly average}} \times 100$$

3.3 To estimate of Cyclical Indices of Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli

Cyclical Indices were calculated for the Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli from the multiplicative model of time series data.

$$\text{Cyclical Indices} = \frac{\text{Original yearly value}}{\text{Estimated trend value}} \times 100$$

$$= T \times C \times I \times 100$$

$$\frac{\quad}{T} = (C \times I) \times 10$$

Where ,

T=Trend

C=Cyclical component

I=Irregular component

To study the relationship between Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli

To Study the relationship between market Arrival and Prices the method of correlation was used. The correlation for the Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli was calculated

correlation worked out by following formula.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\text{Cov } x, y}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

Where,

r = Correlation coefficient

x= Arrival mean.

y = Prices mean.

Cov (x ,y)= Co variance between x and y

σ_x = Standard deviation of x

σ_y = Standard deviation

Result and Discussion

Table 1: The compound growth rate arrival for various major market in case of Dry chilli for, Warangal market (3.46) , Guntur market(2.25), were found positive and most significant at one percent level Byadgi market (0.78)Khammam market (0.9) was significant at five percent level Nandurbar market (0.62) was found non significant in the market. In case of prices Warangal 0.85 , Bydagi 0.73, Guntur 0.49, khammam 0.41, Nandurbar 0.35 were found in most significant and one percent level.

Table 2: In the Guntur market data, for arrivals, the highest coefficient of variation (CV) is 121.60 in 2015, and the lowest is 54.63 in 2017. For prices, the highest CV is 34.74 in 2019, while the lowest is 9.17 in 2016. The Cuddy Della Index (CDI) for arrivals reaches its peak at 101.16 in 2015 and its lowest at 45.44 in 2017, whereas for prices, the highest CDI is 30.38 in 2019, and the lowest is 8.02 in 2016.

Table 3: In the Byadgi market data, for arrivals, the highest coefficient of variation (CV) is 180.04 in 2015, and the lowest is 68.61 in 2020. For prices, the highest CV is 20.65 in 2013, while the lowest is 7.63 in 2019. The Cuddy Della Index (CDI) for arrivals peaks at 175.91 in 2015 and reaches its lowest at 67.03 in 2020, whereas for prices, the highest CDI is 19.95 in 2013, and the lowest is 7.37 in 2019.

In Table 4: The Khammam market data, for arrivals, the highest coefficient of variation (CV) is 155.25 in 2019, and the lowest is 111.34 in 2022. For prices, the highest CV is 40.89 in 2020, while the lowest is 7.35 in 2019. The Cuddy Della Index (CDI) for arrivals reaches its peak at 153.00 in 2019 and its lowest at 109.73 in 2022, while for prices, the highest CDI is 38.02 in 2020, and the lowest is 6.83 in 2019.

Table 5 : In the Warangal market data, for arrivals, the highest coefficient of variation (CV) is 178.76 in 2013, and the lowest is 95.86 in 2022. For prices, the highest CV is 37.52 in 2017, while the lowest is 20.67 in 2022. The Cuddy Della Index (CDI) for arrivals reaches its peak at 154.67 in 2013 and its lowest at 82.94 in 2022, whereas for prices, the highest CDI is 31.42 in 2017, and the lowest is 17.31 in 2022.

Table 6: In the Nandurbar market data, for arrivals, the highest coefficient of variation (CV) is 181.58 in 2013, and the lowest is 121.39 in 2018. For prices, the highest CV is 177.18 in 2016, while the lowest is 24.00 in 2018. The Cuddy Della Index (CDI) for arrivals reaches its peak at 180.91 in 2013 and its lowest at 120.95 in 2018, whereas for prices, the highest CDI is 170.21 in 2016, and the lowest is 23.05 in

Table 7: The data reveals distinct seasonal trends in arrivals across five major markets in India. Guntur peaks in March (208.35) and drops to its lowest in July (62.31), while Byadgi reaches its highest in February (333.34) and falls sharply in July (16.32). Khammam records its highest arrivals in March (347.82) and lowest in September (8.89). Warangal shows a peak in April (286.91) but dips to just 12.23 in July. Nandurbar has the highest arrivals in January (312.19) but experiences a drastic decline by June (0.48)

Table 8: The data reveals notable seasonal variations in Prices across five major markets in India: Guntur, Byadgi, Khammam, Warangal,

and Nandurbar. Guntur experiences the highest Prices in September (114.92) and the lowest in April (77.96), while Byadgi peaks in December (118.43) and dips in July (94.46). Khammam's highest is in February (123.52) and lowest in July (80.30), with Warangal peaking in October (113.75) and bottoming out in June (82.69). Nandurbar stands out with the highest overall Prices in May (144.31) and the lowest in July (67.27), indicating significant fluctuations.

Table 9: The table shows a downward trend in both arrivals and prices from 2012 to 2022, indicating a cyclical variation over the years. The highest number of arrivals was in 2012 at 445.43, while the lowest was in 2022 at 56.32. Prices peaked in 2012 at 153.86 and declined to 74.07 by 2022, reflecting a significant decrease in both metrics over the decade.

Table 10 : The table reveals a consistent decline in both arrivals and prices from 2012 to 2022, indicating a cyclical variation. The highest arrivals occurred in 2012 at 125.20, while the lowest were recorded in 2022 at 83.24. Prices peaked in 2012 at 176.96, decreasing to a low of 69.69 by 2022, highlighting a significant reduction in both metrics over the ten-year span.

Table 11: The table highlights a steady decline in both arrivals and prices from 2012 to 2022, indicating a cyclical variation over the years. Arrivals peaked in 2012 at 218.91 and fell to a low of 64.80 by 2022, while prices also decreased from 143.71 in 2012 to 76.68 in 2022. This consistent downward trend suggests diminishing demand or changing market conditions throughout the decade.

Table 12: The table illustrates a dramatic fluctuation in arrivals and a steady decline in prices from 2012 to 2022. The highest recorded arrivals occurred in 2013 at 1772.68, contrasting sharply with the lowest in 2012 at -557.15. Prices peaked in 2012 at 330.72 but steadily decreased to 58.91 by 2022, indicating a significant drop in both metrics over the decade, particularly after the initial spike in arrivals.

Table 13: The table shows a gradual decline in both arrivals and prices from 2012 to 2022, reflecting a cyclical variation over the years. The highest arrivals were recorded in 2012 at 170.71, while the lowest occurred in 2022 at 70.71. Prices also decreased from a peak of 127.57 in 2012 to 82.23 in 2022, indicating a consistent downward trend in both metrics throughout the decade.

Table 14: The table presents correlation coefficients across five markets (Guntur, Byadgi, Khammam, Warangal, Nandurbar) from 2012 to 2022, indicating varying degrees of positive and negative relationships between them. Guntur displays sporadic positive correlations, particularly notable in 2019 (0.79***), suggesting strong alignment with other markets in that year, while its negative values in other years highlight volatility. Byadgi generally shows consistent positive correlations, particularly in 2013 (0.65**) and 2017 (0.78***), indicating stable relationships with other markets. Khammam stands out with multiple strong positive correlations, especially in 2014 (0.89***) and 2018 (0.68***), reflecting robust market performance. Warangal also has positive correlations, notably in 2018 (0.73***), though it has more negative values, indicating fluctuations. Nandurbar remains mostly negative, with a slight positive correlation in 2019 (0.09ns), suggesting it is less influenced by trends in the other markets. Overall, the data indicates that while some markets experience strong positive relationships, others exhibit instability, reflecting diverse market dynamics over the years.

Table 15: Overall correlation coefficient of arrival and prices of dry chilli in Guntur ,Byadgi ,Khammam , Warangal and Nandurbar markets.

The correlation coefficients in the table indicate the degree of relationship between the markets, with values reflecting varying strengths. Guntur (0.29ns) and Byadgi (0.14ns) show relatively weak correlations, suggesting limited alignment with other markets. In contrast, Khammam (0.40*) and Warangal (0.43*) exhibit moderate positive correlations, indicating a more significant relationship with market trends. Nandurbar, with a coefficient of 0.70ns, shows a notable

correlation but is marked as non-significant, implying that while it may align positively with others, the relationship lacks statistical strength.

Conclusion

1. The Compound Growth Rate (CGR) analysis indicates significant growth in arrivals and prices for Guntur and Warangal, with CGRs of 2.25% and 3.46% for arrivals, respectively. This suggests robust market activity and potential for future expansion in these regions, highlighting them as key players in the dry chili market.

2. The coefficient of variation (CV) analysis reveals considerable fluctuations in arrivals and prices across all markets. Guntur, Byadgi, Khammam, Warangal, and Nandurbar each exhibited periods of high variability, reflecting the impact of regional factors and market instability on supply and pricing.

3. Seasonal variations in arrivals demonstrate distinct monthly trends influenced by local supply-demand dynamics. Each market exhibits unique peak and low months, with Guntur peaking in March and Nandurbar in January, indicating that understanding these patterns can aid in better inventory management and pricing strategies.

4. The cyclical nature of the dry chili market, stabilizing around 2017, indicates ongoing adjustments in market conditions. While all markets experienced declines in arrivals and prices from 2012 to 2022, understanding these cycles can provide insights for future market predictions and strategies.

5. The correlation analysis between arrivals and prices highlights varied relationships across markets. Guntur and Byadgi show stable positive correlations, while Nandurbar primarily exhibits negative correlations, suggesting that external factors may affect its market dynamics more significantly than in other regions.

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Table 1: Compound Growth Rates in Arrival and Prices of Dry Chili in Major Markets of India (2012-22):

Major markets	Arrival		Prices	
	CGR	t value	CGR	t value
Guntur	2.25***	7.6	0.49***	6.32
Byadgi	0.78**	2.49	0.73***	16.14
Khammam	0.9**	1.96	0.41***	4.52
Warangal	3.46***	6.6	0.85***	7.44
Nandurbar	0.62 ^{ns}	0.98	0.35***	3.29

Table 2 Coefficient of variation (C.V.) and variability for Arrival and Prices of Dry Chili in Guntur market (2012-2023)

Year	Arrival		Prices	
	CV(%)	CDI(%)	CV(%)	CDI(%)
2012	113.308	94.26	9.83	8.60
2013	96.54	80.30	16.95	14.83

2014	116.14	96.61	10.20	8.92
2015	121.60	101.16	16.90	14.78
2016	68.09	56.64	9.17	8.02
2017	54.63	45.44	24.48	21.41
2018	56.38	46.90	24.79	21.68
2019	66.06	54.95	34.74	30.38
2020	75.93	63.16	26.88	23.51
2021	55.33	46.02	23.17	20.26
2022	55.08	45.82	18.02	15.76

Table 3 Coefficient of variation (C.V.) and variability for Arrival and Prices of Dry Chili in Byadgi market (2012-2023)

Year	Arrival		Prices	
	CV(%)	CDI(%)	CV(%)	CDI(%)
2012	119.62	116.87	12.28	11.86
2013	110.17	107.64	20.65	19.95
2014	110.86	108.31	12.49	12.06
2015	180.04	175.91	10.15	9.81
2016	116.84	114.16	9.85	9.51
2017	119.16	116.42	15.47	14.94
2018	107.39	104.93	8.21	7.93
2019	129.50	126.53	7.63	7.37
2020	68.61	67.03	16.56	15.99
2021	107.52	105.05	17.26	16.67
2022	135.59	132.47	18.65	18.01

Table 4 Coefficient of variation (C.V.) and variability for Arrival and Prices of Dry Chili in Khammam market (2012-2023)

Year	Arrival		Prices	
	CV(%)	CDI(%)	CV(%)	CDI(%)
2012	133.34	131.41	14.78	13.74
2013	114.08	112.43	29.38	27.31
2014	142.95	140.88	12.89	11.98
2015	131.56	129.65	11.99	11.15
2016	149.60	147.43	11.45	10.65
2017	116.92	115.23	37.32	34.70
2018	135.43	133.47	10.93	10.16
2019	155.25	153.00	7.35	6.83
2020	155.12	152.87	40.89	38.02
2021	129.69	127.80	34.83	32.39
2022	111.34	109.73	20.47	19.03

Table 5. Coefficient of variation (C.V.) and variability for Arrival and Prices of Dry Chili in Warangal market (2012-2023)

Year	Arrival		Prices	
	CV(%)	CDI(%)	CV(%)	CDI(%)
2012	152.14	131.63	23.43	19.62
2013	178.76	154.67	27.27	22.84
2014	137.36	118.85	30.36	25.43
2015	143.34	124.02	27.55	23.07
2016	117.93	102.03	36.41	30.49
2017	157.07	135.90	37.52	31.42
2018	153.94	133.19	24.48	20.50
2019	131.37	113.66	31.07	26.02
2020	139.74	120.90	24.18	20.25
2021	135.01	116.82	24.38	20.42

2022	95.86	82.94	20.67	17.31
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Table 6 Coefficient of variation (C.V.) and variability for Arrival and Prices of Dry Chili in Nandurbar market (2012-2023)

Year	Arrival		Prices	
	CV(%)	CDI(%)	CV(%)	CDI(%)
2012	132.89	132.41	43.88	42.15
2013	181.58	180.91	71.34	68.53
2014	122.96	122.51	28.01	26.90
2015	136.71	136.21	57.81	55.54
2016	157.26	156.69	177.18	170.21
2017	159.68	159.09	50.17	48.20
2018	121.39	120.95	24.00	23.05
2019	152.34	151.78	30.15	28.96
2020	164.5	163.90	41.51	39.88
2021	125.71	125.25	60.05	57.69
2022	148.76	148.21	65.04	62.48

Table 7 Seasonal Indices of Arrivals of Dry Chilli in major markets of India (2012-22).

Months	Guntur	Byadgi	Khammam	Warangal	Nandurbar
January	115.42	241.13	109.09	46.76	312.19
February	189.18	333.34	241.68	222.46	152.42
March	208.35	259.38	347.82	312.88	56.32
April	190.11	122.77	283.40	286.91	15.43
May	73.20	34.08	97.34	166.85	2.23
June	63.69	21.20	34.86	50.20	0.48
July	62.31	16.32	19.75	12.23	1.35
August	63.99	15.20	16.21	16.57	0.41
September	47.53	16.01	8.89	14.33	22.32
October	53.99	16.21	6.30	13.94	144.17
November	59.02	32.17	7.01	16.40	213.09
December	73.21	92.20	27.65	40.48	279.58

Table 8. Seasonal indices of Prices of Dry Chilli in major markets of India (2012-22).

Months	Guntur	Byadgi	Khammam	Warangal	Nandurbar
January	89.27	105.76	106.73	83.29	79.65
February	95.51	106.96	123.52	105.35	78.68
March	91.95	102.85	117.53	113.30	86.90
April	77.96	93.03	104.99	99.64	103.07
May	83.08	93.48	105.65	83.26	144.31
June	97.47	95.28	92.46	82.69	156.94
July	102.50	94.46	90.30	98.72	67.27
August	107.05	93.60	84.31	100.27	123.25
September	114.92	97.45	82.42	104.30	90.41
October	111.44	94.82	80.43	113.75	83.08
November	115.03	103.88	90.85	97.76	93.13
December	113.82	118.43	120.81	117.66	93.32

Table 9 Cyclical indices of Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli in Guntur market (2012-2022)

Year	Arrival	Prices
2012	445.43	153.86
2013	263.43	138.90
2014	187.02	126.59
2015	144.97	116.28
2016	118.36	107.53
2017	100.00	100.00
2018	86.57	93.46
2019	76.32	87.72

2020	68.25	82.64
2021	61.71	78.12
2022	56.32	74.07

Table 10 Cyclical indices of Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli in Byagdi market (2012-2022)

Year	Arrival	Prices
2012	125.20	176.96
2013	119.19	153.36
2014	113.74	135.31
2015	108.76	121.06
2016	104.19	109.53
2017	100.00	100.00
2018	96.13	92.00
2019	92.55	85.18
2020	89.22	79.31
2021	86.13	74.19
2022	83.24	69.69

Table 11 Cyclical indices of Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli in Khammam market (2012-2022)

Year	Arrival	Prices
2012	218.91	143.71
2013	176.85	132.16
2014	148.35	122.32
2015	127.76	113.85
2016	112.19	106.48
2017	100.00	100.00
2018	90.20	94.27
2019	82.15	89.15
2020	75.42	84.57
2021	69.71	80.43
2022	64.80	76.68

Table 12 Cyclical indices of Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli in Warangal market (2012-2022)

Year	Arrival	Prices
2012	-557.15	330.72
2013	1772.68	226.30
2014	342.10	171.99
2015	189.32	138.71
2016	130.87	116.22
2017	100.00	100.00
2018	80.91	87.76
2019	67.94	78.18
2020	58.56	70.49
2021	51.45	64.18
2022	45.88	58.91

Table 13 Cyclical indices of Arrival and Prices of Dry Chilli in Nandurbar market (2012-2022)

Year	Arrival	Prices
2012	170.71	127.57
2013	149.56	120.90
2014	133.07	114.90
2015	119.86	109.46
2016	109.03	104.52
2017	100.00	100.00
2018	92.35	95.86
2019	85.79	92.04

2020	80.09	88.52
2021	75.11	85.26
2022	70.71	82.23

Table 14 Correlation coefficient of arrival and prices of Dry Chilli in Five major market in India

Years	Guntur	Byadgi	Khammam	Warangal	Nandurbar
2012	0.46*	0.35 ^{ns}	0.72***	-0.24 ^{ns}	-0.28 ^{ns}
2013	-0.33 ^{ns}	0.65**	0.46*	0.10 ^{ns}	-0.36 ^{ns}
2014	-0.69 ^{ns}	0.54**	0.89***	-0.13 ^{ns}	-0.15 ^{ns}
2015	-0.13 ^{ns}	0.46*	-0.22 ^{ns}	-0.49 ^{ns}	-0.28 ^{ns}
2016	-0.20 ^{ns}	0.11 ^{ns}	0.62**	0.03 ^{ns}	-0.44 ^{ns}
2017	-0.11 ^{ns}	0.78***	0.21 ^{ns}	-0.04 ^{ns}	-0.20 ^{ns}
2018	-0.37 ^{ns}	0.63**	0.68***	0.73***	-0.09 ^{ns}
2019	0.79***	0.02 ^{ns}	0.48*	-0.28 ^{ns}	0.09 ^{ns}
2020	-0.57 ^{ns}	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.42*	0.08 ^{ns}	0.01 ^{ns}
2021	-0.10 ^{ns}	0.53**	0.05 ^{ns}	0.41*	-0.40 ^{ns}
2022	-0.75 ^{ns}	-0.30 ^{ns}	0.44*	0.15 ^{ns}	-0.09 ^{ns}

Table 15 Correlation coefficient of arrival and prices of Dry Chilli in Five Major Markets (2012-2022)

Sr. no.	Markets	Correlation coefficient (CV%)
1	Guntur	0.29 ^{ns}
2	Byadgi	0.14 ^{ns}
3	Khammam	0.40*
4	Warangal	0.43*
5	Nandurbar	0.70 ^{ns}